

Creating a Security Enforcement Environment for a Vehicular Platform

Marinos Tsantekidis*, Souleima Abdelghani†, Mohammad Hamad†, and Vassilis Prevelakis‡

* AEGIS IT RESEARCH GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany

† Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany

‡ Technical University of Braunschweig, Braunschweig, Germany

Email: *m.tsantekidis@aegisresearch.eu, † {firstname.lastname}@tum.de ‡ prevelakis@ida.ing.tu-bs.de

Abstract—The ever-increasing complexity of automotive platforms combined with the introduction of commercial off-the-shelf software components (e.g., for the entertainment system) creates multiple attack vectors that adversaries can leverage to attack the platform. Traditional analysis techniques have difficulty dealing with such complex environments, especially considering the need for low-cost solutions. Hence, we propose in this paper to turn the logic around, and instead of trying to discover all possible vulnerabilities, we monitor the execution of a software system to ensure that it does not deviate from its nominal profile. In this paper, we demonstrate a technique for creating a state model mapping the execution of a system, and then by observing its interaction with the runtime environment through its invocation of various library functions, we can ensure that off-nominal behavior can be detected and acted upon. The valuation results provide further evidence of the wrapper mechanism’s effectiveness and highlight its potential to enhance security while minimizing the impact on performance.

Index Terms—Security, Software Intrusion Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Today’s vehicles consist of numerous small computers, each referred to as an Electronic Control Unit (ECU), interconnected through various types of networks and hosting a massive number of software components that offer diverse functionalities and services. Many Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) try to build such software components in-house or get it from other suppliers [1]. To reduce the development timelines and costs, many of OEMs utilize software components from other industries or use commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) software components for many sub-systems within the vehicle [2]. Examples of such systems where COTS software components can be utilized include infotainment and ADAS systems. The high connectivity of the vehicle system makes access to such software components possible, which could open up a massive attack surface against the entire system [3]. This is particularly concerning when we consider that such components were not originally developed to meet the automotive domain’s high security and safety requirements. So, it’s critical to provide mechanisms to detect when these software components are behaving maliciously.

Related work: Numerous approaches have been proposed to detect the off-nominal behavior of software components. One of these approaches involves utilizing *Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)* to ensure the isolation of software components from each other and the operating system. [4].

However, employing such a technique necessitates specialized hardware and software. Moreover, TEEs might not be compatible with all software types and could demand further development efforts for seamless integration with existing systems.

Trace-based analysis is a technique utilized to model the behavior of software components and subsequently identify vulnerabilities that may exist within these components [5]. Within the realm of automotive systems, examining the traces of temporal behavior exhibited by software components across multiple executions can be employed to ascertain whether the software has been compromised in the event of any departure from this established behavior [6]. Nonetheless, this approach does come with limitations: the attacker might succeed in compromising the software component without necessarily surpassing the worst-case execution time of the task, particularly when we consider that the time constraint is often overapproximated [7].

Another approach is to monitor software behavior at the operating system level using *system calls* [8], their sequence [9], as well as their frequency [10]. This approach involves monitoring a program’s calls to the operating system at the lowest level, collecting these system calls and learning the system’s normal behavior. Then any deviation from this normal distribution of system call frequencies behavior can be detected and used as a sign of off-nominal execution. However, this approach has its limitations. The model of normal behavior may not be accurate, leading to false positive or false negative results. Furthermore, attackers can adapt their malicious behavior to be more similar to normal behavior, making it difficult for the intrusion detection mechanism to accurately distinguish between normal and malicious behavior [11]. Additionally, system call monitoring only provides limited visibility of program behavior, as it does not consider the interactions between the program and the underlying libraries it uses. Furthermore, the fine-grain control of the low-level system calls offered by this approach may result in a multitude of checks when higher-level calls (e.g. library calls) are made. Checking calls required by system or user level libraries when implementing complex operations would be overly verbose and not only unnecessary, but undesired too.

One approach to monitoring a software component using the interactions with libraries is proposed in [12], [13], where

a framework is introduced to monitor the *network-based behavior* of software components in ECUs by tracing the network-related calls in the `libc` library that the applications might utilize. This approach establishes a degree of compartmentalization within the ECUs and the in-vehicle network. However, this approach is constrained to detecting malicious activities linked to communication-based actions and may not be as effective in identifying or preventing other forms of malicious behavior.

Contribution: To address the limitations of existing work, careful consideration must be given to selecting the appropriate level for implementing the monitoring mechanism. This paper aims to model the behavior of software components through the calls they make. However, our approach differs from the traditional low-level perspective (e.g., [8]–[10]); instead, it emphasizes a higher level of abstraction: library calls. Moreover, unlike the approach in [12], [13], our objective is to encompass all utilized libraries. The primary contribution of this research is the creation of a state machine that represents the nominal behavior of the software component. This is achieved by intercepting library function invocations made by the application and constructing a comprehensive profile. This profile subsequently enables the detection and prevention of deviations from nominal behavior during runtime, thereby indicating vulnerabilities or intentional attacks. To facilitate the creation and enforcement of these profiles, we develop library wrappers. Each wrapper offers a straightforward and effective method for building the application’s state machine. The same wrapper will subsequently be employed to monitor the behavior of the application, ensuring the prevention of any divergence from its nominal behavior. Specifically, the paper makes the following contributions:

- It introduces an approach that emphasizes modeling software behavior through higher-level abstraction, specifically focusing on library calls (Section II).
- It proposes a method using intercepted library functions to create a state machine that enables runtime detection of deviations, vulnerabilities, and intentional attacks within a unified wrapper (section III).
- It implements and evaluates the proposed solution and demonstrates its effectiveness and efficiency by analyzing real-world application (Section IV and V).

II. LIBRARY LEVEL ACCESS CONTROL

Access control, in a narrow sense, is the ability of a system to grant or reject access to a protected resource. This way, in the context of software security, the system can keep track of who has access to what code, who can call what function in a library and under which conditions this is possible. These restrictions are imposed by a set of mandatory controls that are enforced by the system in the form of security policies.

In this work, we present a mechanism that allows access control policies for library calls to be enforced at the user-code level in order to restrict access to functions held in a protected library, in addition to identifying the complete execution path regarding the functions in question. Our work builds upon

Fig. 1. State machine representation illustrating the categorization of library call types into states.

earlier work presented in [14], where we outline a system that implements security policies at the library call level by wrapping libraries and directing external function calls to a policy enforcement engine. This innovative approach helps to secure applications from security threats and vulnerabilities by controlling access to the underlying system resources and functions. Under our approach, a call is intercepted before it reaches its destination. There, we have a chance to analyze the arguments of the call. Moreover, this is the point where we apply security policies, before allowing the call to move ahead. By doing this, we can detect any deviations from a predefined behavioral profile of the application under test (see Section III). The research presented in this paper takes a similar approach, but goes a step further by using the wrapper library not only for security policy checks, but also for modeling the application behavior. This enables us to gain a deeper understanding of the interactions between the application and the underlying system, allowing us to identify potential security risks and vulnerabilities.

Furthermore, our mechanism cooperates seamlessly with our kernel-based approach [15], where we propose another technique to deal with not only dynamically linked applications, but also statically linked applications. This technique involves adding code to the kernel to monitor when user code invokes a library function in a computer program. The added code determines whether the call should go ahead, checks the acceptability of the arguments and informs the kernel when the code returns from the called function. This approach provides a comprehensive way of securing the application, including both dynamically and statically linked libraries.

III. STATE MACHINE

For this mechanism to be effective we need to have a comprehensive model of the program behavior and in particular not only which library calls are being made during the execution of the program, but at what *stage* of the execution the call was made. In this way we can identify attacks that leverage facilities that the program utilizes anyway, but at a different phase of the execution. We do this by grouping calls according to the *state* that the program is in. Each state includes a group

of calls belonging to a single library and related to each other, as shown in Fig. 1. This approach results in the representation of the software component as a comprehensive state machine composed of a finite number of states.

By grouping the different types of library calls into states, we can accurately reflect the different phases that the software component undergoes as it executes. This representation allows us later to detect anomalies or deviations from the expected behavior, which can indicate an intrusion. The state machine serves as a blueprint of what the application should be doing at any given time, and any deviation from this blueprint can trigger an alarm for further investigation. This way, we can ensure that the application is executing as expected and that no unexpected library calls are made that could potentially harm the system.

To create this state representation, it's essential to capture all the library calls that the software will execute. To accomplish this, we developed a mechanism involving a wrapper library. This library is positioned between the application and the original library code. The wrapper library is designed to intercept every library function call initiated by the application, recording the pertinent details. The recording process logs crucial data, such as the library's name and the used function. This data is logged as tuples, including the function's name (e.g., `strcmp()`) and the corresponding library's name (e.g., `libc`). To gather as much information as possible about the application's behavior, we employed fuzzing techniques to generate and send hundreds of random inputs that fulfilled the application's requirements.

In the following sections, we describe how we construct the state machine representation of software components. The entire process is illustrated in Fig. 2. To illustrate this approach, we use the web server *bozohhttpd*¹ as a case study. Bozohhttpd is a compact and secure HTTP version 1.1 server that is widely used in various operating systems, particularly those designed for constrained devices.

A. Wrapper Library Development

We can use the command line tool `ldd` to determine which shared libraries a specific application requires. This powerful tool allows one to see the dependencies of a particular binary file. After running the `ldd` command along with our executable bozohhttpd server as input, we can see many libraries (e.g., `linux-vdso`, `ld-linux`, `libcrypto`, `libssl` and `libc`) have been reported. The shared dependencies `linuxvdso` and `ld-linux` required by the application are indirect dependencies. `Linux-vdso` (virtual dynamic shared object) is a small shared library that the kernel automatically maps into the address space of all user-space applications. The `ld-linux` programs locate and load the shared objects (shared libraries) needed by the program, prepare the program for execution, and then run it. As a result, `libcrypto`, `libssl` and `libc` are the only relevant libraries in our case.

After obtaining the software component's shared library dependencies, we need to further analyze these libraries to

Fig. 2. The process of generating the application's state machine using wrapper library.

find out all the function information that are included in each library. One can use the `readelf` command-line tool to do so. The option `-dyn-syms` can display the dynamic symbols in a symbol table. These symbols are used by shared libraries at run-time and are resolved by the dynamic linker when the program is run. By adding the `-W` option, more information about the symbols can be displayed, such as their size and binding. The list of the function names is then saved to a file, with one file per library.

Then, to record the library function calls made by the application at run-time, we develop wrapper functions or a wrapper library, depending on whether we have access to the source code of the application. If the application is open-source, then we can develop wrapper functions for each matched function identified by the previously discussed bash script. These wrapper functions record the invocation of the original library function before calling it, allowing for monitoring of external library usage. All matched functions are renamed with the prefix `wr-` to ensure that the application uses the wrapper functions. Listing 1 is an example of using the wrapper for the `memcpy` function.

```

1 void *wr_memcpy(void *__restrict dest, const
2   void *__restrict src, size_t n)
3 {
4     // Log the original call and the library
5     printf("Function: memcpy, Library:
6         libc\n");
7     // Call the original library function
8     memcpy(dest, src, n);
9 }

```

Listing 1. Custom memcpy

This approach allows the original library function to be called within the wrapper function while providing a hook for recording the call. The wrapper functions can be implemented in a separate source file and linked to the application during compilation, providing a modular approach that can be easily integrated into the existing code base.

On the other hand, if there is no access to the source code of the application, we can use a more generic approach, in order

¹<http://www.eterna.com.au/bozohhttpd/>

to create a wrapper for the whole library. To that end, we extract all the relevant functions and their signatures from the header files of a library. The extraction is performed using a custom Python script that identifies each function and analyzes its arguments. This way we are able to manipulate each of the arguments in any way necessary. Before calling the originally intended function, we add code that verifies that the module, indeed, captured the call and that we operate from within the custom library. After that, the execution flow progresses to the original path. An example of a wrapped function can be seen in Listing 2 (SHA1 from the OpenSSL library).

```

1 typedef unsigned char
2     (*original_SHA1_type)(const unsigned
3     char *d, size_t n, unsigned char *md);
4 unsigned char *SHA1(const unsigned char *d,
5     size_t n, unsigned char *md)
6 {
7     // Log the original call and the library
8     printf("Function: SHA1, Library:
9     libssl\n");
10    original_SHA1_type original_SHA1;
11    original_SHA1 = (original_SHA1_type)
12        dlsym(RTLD_NEXT, "SHA1");
13    return original_SHA1(d, n, md);
14 }

```

Listing 2. Wrapped SHA1 function from the OpenSSL library

The wrapper library is implemented in a separate source file and compiled into a shared object file. It can then be linked to the executable we want to monitor. From this point forward, when the application (e.g. bozohttpd) makes a call to the SHA1 function, our wrapper version will be executed first.

B. State Machine Development

As mentioned earlier, our objective is to create a comprehensive state machine that accurately represents the behavior of the targeted software component. To achieve this, it is crucial to engage with the component in a manner that covers all possible execution paths. This necessitates supplying various inputs that can trigger different execution paths. We believe that the fuzzing technique could assist us in generating such inputs. Fuzzing is a software testing approach involving the submission of random or unconventional data inputs to a designated system—in our case, the bozohttpd web server. Its purpose is to uncover security vulnerabilities, uncover compatibility problems, or reveal unexpected behavior. Fuzzing is also effective in gauging how the server reacts to various inputs. Dispatching a multitude of arbitrary or specifically designed inputs to the server and evaluating its corresponding outputs can provide valuable insights into the software component's behavior. Using fuzzing, we created a list of 200 payloads, which are relative URL paths that can be added to the server's base URL. Throughout every execution, we utilize the implemented wrapper mechanism to record each invoked library call.

Listing 3 shows the outcome of this process, where we can see that the library calls are integrated into the response generated by the bozohttpd server. By analyzing the 200

responses, we are able to identify various types of behaviors that the bozohttpd server exhibits, such as CGI processing, redirection, normal file processing and errors.

```

1 ...
2 Function: sigemptyset, Library: Libc
3 Function: sigaddset, Library: Libc
4 Function: sigaction, Library: Libc
5 Function: clock_gettime, Library: Libc
6 Function: alarm, Library: Libc
7 Function: malloc, Library: Libc
8 Function: read, Library: Libc
9 ...
10 latexHTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
11 Function: vprintf, Library: Libc
12 content-type: text/html
13 Function: vprintf, Library: Libc
14 Content-Length: 213
15 Function: vprintf, Library: Libc
16 Server: boxohhttpd/20201014

```

Listing 3. Library calls integrated into the bozohttpd response

To ensure that the state machine accurately represents the server's behavior, we link each state to a list containing specific types of library calls. For example, state A is designed to expect only read(), sigemptyset(), sigaddset() and sigaction() library calls.

This helps guarantee that no additional calls will be made in each state and that the state machine accurately represents the server's behavior. Once the state machine is created, we adjust our wrapper functions for run-time policy enforcement (Listing 4 and Listing 5). This involves adding a policy check

```

1 void *wr_memcpy(void *__restrict dest, const
2 void *__restrict src, size_t n){
3     update_state("memcpy");
4     if(!check_in_set("memcpy",
5         current_state_list[current_state],
6         num_calls_per_state[current_state])){
7         // stop the web server
8         printf("Error: Policy Violation");
9         exit(2);
10    }
11    // call the original library function
12    memcpy(dest,src,n);
13 }

```

Listing 4. Policy check when source code is available

```

1 unsigned char *SHA1(const unsigned char *d,
2 size_t n, unsigned char *md){
3     update_state("SHA1");
4     if(!check_in_set("SHA1",
5         current_state_list[current_state],
6         num_calls_per_state[current_state])){
7         // stop the web server
8         printf("Error: Policy Violation");
9         exit(2);
10    }
11    original_SHA1_type original_SHA1;
12    original_SHA1 = (original_SHA1_type)
13        dlsym(RTLD_NEXT, "SHA1");
14    return original_SHA1(d, n, md);
15 }

```

Listing 5. Policy check when source code is not available

Fig. 3. Comparison of logs from the protected (black) and non-protected (gray and black) bozohtp servers during testing with a malicious URL input.

to the wrapper library/function to ensure that each library call is compared to the elements of the list representing the current state that is part of state machine that accurately reflects the behavior of the application.

IV. SECURITY ANALYSIS

To assess the effectiveness of our proposed mechanisms, we deliberately introduced a vulnerability into the bozohtp server. This vulnerability is triggered when the URL included %77, causing the server to connect to another server and compromise the `/etc/passwd` file. This simulated attack on the server allowed us to gauge its behavior. To further analyze the response of protected and unprotected applications under this attack, we conducted two scenarios: one with the wrapper mechanism implemented and another without. Subsequently, we sent requests containing URLs with %77 to observe and compare the server’s behavior in each case.

The results of our analysis are shown in Fig. 3. When the unprotected application was subjected to the attack, it executed all the library calls as expected, compromising the `/etc/passwd` file. This attack could potentially allow an attacker to gain unauthorized access to the system. On the other hand, the protected application detected the attack and prevented it from causing harm. Our detection point was at the socket library call, which is the point where the server’s behavior deviated from nominal behavior and connected to the malicious server. In the protected application, this call triggered a policy violation, invoking the exit function and preventing the application from connecting. The grayed-out section of Fig. 3 indicates the calls that were blocked by our protection mechanism. As a result, the protected application remained safe from the attack, and its behavior was significantly different from that of the unprotected application.

Fig. 4. The performance evaluation of bozohtp with and without wrapper mechanism.

However, this approach is essentially another shared library loaded into the program at run-time at the user space. An advanced attacker could be able to bypass it and circumvent the policy enforcement step. Randomization techniques [16], [17], as well as hardening approaches at the kernel side (as mentioned is Section II) work in parallel to this user-level approach, making it much more difficult for an adversary to bypass the security policy evaluation.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In order to measure the overhead of our proposed mechanism, we implement a bash script that issues HTTP requests to a running bozohtp server on an embedded system with Quad-core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC working at a speed of 1.8 GHz. Using the script, we aim to measure the execution time of the protected application with and without our wrapper mechanism. The script sends ten sequences of 2000 requests per sequence using `wget` command line tool. We measure the time required to send the request, receive the response, and close the connection for each request.

As can be seen in Fig. 4, our analysis showed that the wrapper mechanism had a minimal impact on the execution time of the protected application. The average response time for the protected application with the wrapper mechanism was only slightly higher than that of the unprotected application, ranging from 5% to 20%. This indicates that our wrapper mechanism is small and does not significantly impact the performance of the protected application. These results show that our wrapper mechanism provides an additional layer of security without compromising the performance of the protected application.

Also, we evaluated the memory usage of our approach when compared to the bozohtp application without our mechanism. We achieved that using the `pmap` command-line tool, which determines the memory map of the processes used in the application. The memory map shows the memory regions allocated to the process and their properties. In the case of using the bozohtp server without our wrapper mechanism, the total memory allocated to the application is 7868 kB. This memory includes the process itself, shared

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF MEMORY USAGE WITH AND WITHOUT OUR MECHANISM

Library/Process	Original (kB)	Our Solution (kB)
bozohttpd	92	124
libc.so.6	2156	2156
libcrypto.so.3	4352	4352
libssl.so.3	656	656
ld-linux-x86-64.so.2	236	236
anon	244	244
stack	132	132
Total	7868	7900

libraries used by the application and anonymous memory regions. In both cases, the largest memory allocation is to the `libcrypto.so.3` shared library, which uses 4352kB of memory. The `libc.so.6` and `libssl.so.3` shared libraries also use a significant amount of memory, 2156 kB and 656 kB, respectively. The anonymous memory region, which is used for dynamically allocated memory, uses 244kB of memory. As you can see in Table I, the results indicated that the increase in memory usage only occurred in the `bozohttpd` process itself, increasing from 92kB to 124kB due to the added wrapper library. However, the other memory regions remained the same size as before. This outcome was expected since the wrapper code we added was compiled alongside the application code before execution. Overall, the increase in memory usage was small, with an increase of 32kB or approximately 0.4%. This increase is well within the acceptable range for most applications, especially those running on modern hardware with sufficient memory capacity. Therefore, our mechanism is a viable option for improving the security of computer programs without causing excessive memory usage.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have proposed an approach for software component intrusion detection. The approach was realized by developing a wrapper library mechanism to intercept library calls and enforce run-time policy checks. Our approach enables us to monitor the system execution and modify its functionality if any suspicious activity is detected. We demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach by introducing a vulnerability in the `bozohttpd` web server and attempting to exploit it. Our evaluation shows the effectiveness of our wrapper in detecting and preventing attacks on software applications with minimal performance impact.

Limitations and future work: The current wrapper code implementation incorporates a state machine that characterizes the application’s typical behavior, yet this limits the code’s reusability, as it requires modification for each application it is used with. Therefore, we propose that future work should focus on decoupling the application profile from the wrapper code, ensuring its adaptability across various applications without any need for modifications. Also, our evaluation of the wrapper mechanism was limited to a single application (`Bozohttpd`). Although this application is extensively used, assessing our mechanism across a broader range of applications

would be advantageous to ascertain its effectiveness in a more comprehensive context. Such evaluation would enhance the understanding of the wrapper mechanism’s potential and its capacity to offer robust protection against diverse attacks. Finally, our mechanism currently supports C-written applications due to the focus on C libraries. Future work could expand the approach to encompass more programming languages.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the following European Union-funded projects: a) JCOP (Agreement No.: INEA/CE-F/ICT/A2020/2373266), b) CyberSecPro (Agreement No.: 101083594), c) SecOPERA (Agreement No.: 101070599) and d) CyberSecDome (Agreement No.: 101120779)

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Fletcher, A. Mahindroo, N. Santhanam, and A. Tschiesner, “The case for an end-to-end automotive-software platform,” *McKinsey & Company*, vol. 16, 2020.
- [2] K. Huang, B. Hu, L. Chen, A. Knoll, and Z. Wang, “Adas on cots with opencl: a case study with lane detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 559–565, 2017.
- [3] M. Hamad and V. Prevelakis, “SAVTA: A hybrid vehicular threat model: Overview and case study,” *Information*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 273, 2020.
- [4] S. W. Kim, C. Lee, M. Jeon, H. Y. Kwon, H. W. Lee, and C. Yoo, “Secure device access for automotive software,” in *2013 International Conference on Connected Vehicles and Expo (ICCVE)*, 2013.
- [5] C. Colby and P. Lee, “Trace-based program analysis,” in *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGPLAN-SIGACT symposium on Principles of programming languages*, 1996, pp. 195–207.
- [6] A. Bucaioni, E. Ferko, and H. Lönn, “Trace-based timing analysis of automotive software systems: an experience report,” in *2021 ACM/IEEE International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems Companion (MODELS-C)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 254–263.
- [7] M. Hamad, Z. A. Hammadeh, S. Saida, V. Prevelakis, and R. Ernst, “Prediction of abnormal temporal behavior in real-time systems,” in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*, 2018.
- [8] N. Provos, “Improving host security with system call policies,” in *Proceedings of the 12th Conference on USENIX Security Symposium - Volume 12*, ser. SSYM’03. Berkeley, CA, USA: USENIX Association, 2003.
- [9] S. A. Hofmeyr, S. Forrest, and A. Somayaji, “Intrusion detection using sequences of system calls,” *Journal of computer security*, vol. 6, 1998.
- [10] M.-K. Yoon, S. Mohan, J. Choi, M. Christodorescu, and L. Sha, “Learning execution contexts from system call distribution for anomaly detection in smart embedded system,” in *2017 IEEE/ACM Second International Conference on Internet-of-Things Design and Implementation*, 2017.
- [11] D. Wagner and P. Soto, “Mimicry attacks on host-based intrusion detection systems,” in *Proceedings of the 9th ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2002, pp. 255–264.
- [12] M. Hamad, M. Nolte, and V. Prevelakis, “A framework for policy based secure intra vehicle communication,” in *2017 IEEE Vehicular Networking Conference (VNC)*, 2017, pp. 1–8.
- [13] M. Hamad, J. Schlatow, V. Prevelakis, and R. Ernst, “A communication framework for distributed access control in microkernel-based systems,” in *12th Annual Workshop on Operating Systems Platforms for Embedded Real-Time Applications (OSPERT16)*, 2016.
- [14] M. Tsantekidis and V. Prevelakis, “Library-Level Policy Enforcement,” in *The Eleventh International Conference on Emerging Security Information, Systems and Technologies (SECURWARE)*, 2017.
- [15] —, “Efficient Monitoring of Library Call Invocation,” in *Sixth International Conference on Internet of Things: Systems, Management and Security (IOTSMS)*, Granada, Spain, 2019.
- [16] T. PaX, “Address Space Layout Randomization,” <https://pax.grsecurity.net/docs/aslr.txt>, 2001.
- [17] H. Marco-Gisbert and I. Ripoll Ripoll, “Address space layout randomization next generation,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 14, 2019.